

HYPERTENSIVES AND MEDICAL MANAGEMENT: ARE THEY SILENT CONTRIBUTORS TO THE BURDEN OF LUNG DISEASE IN OUR SOCIETY

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Background and objectives: Hypertension is increasing globally with another 60% expected increase by 2025. In spite of advancing research and different classes of anti-hypertensive medications (anti-HT), not all of them can be branded safe. Pulmonary complications of different classes of anti-HT were unexplored in South India. Our aim is to compare PFT among hypertensive (HT) & healthy controls and also among HT taking various classes of anti-HT. **Methods:** Case control study. Age-matched healthy controls (n=91) HT cases (n=93) randomly selected. Group I Beta blockers (n= 14), Group II Calcium Channel blockers (n= 18), Group III Angiotensin receptor blockers (n=23), Group IV drug combinations (n= 38). Anthropometry taken, BP recorded, PFT assessed using Easyone Spirometer and data analysed using ANOVA and Student “t” test. **Results:** Study results show statistically significant reduction in PFT values in all groups of cases and also in females. Out of 93 cases, 49 normal PFT, 7 obstructions, 5 restrictions, 32 mixed airway disease. PFT statistically significantly reduced among various classes of anti-HT, FVC (p=0.026), FEV1 (p=0.000), PEF (p=0.038). **Interpretation & Conclusion:** We conclude reduction in PFT among HT taking various common classes of anti-HT and hence recommend periodic evaluation of PFT in all HT patients.

Key words: Hypertension, anti-hypertensive medications, pulmonary function tests

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Introduction:

Hypertension is increasing globally with a 60% expected increase by 2025 totalling to 1.56 billion¹ and needless to say it is very rampant in India also. Hypertension is a disease that affects the body as a whole. Various complications of hypertension that are well documented are congestive cardiac failure, stroke, retinopathy and nephropathy²⁻⁶. Today, in India, treatment of hypertension includes anti-hypertensive medications, life style modification, salt-restricted diet, and treatment of complications, if any. Voluminous research in pharmacology has helped in the introduction of newer drugs in addition to the existing classes of anti-hypertensive medications. In addition to sudden drastic fall in BP, anti-hypertensive medications produces many undesirable sides-effects. To mention some, headache (caused by ACE inhibitors, Calcium Channel Blockers, Alpha blockers), frequent urination (beta blockers and diuretics) increased cold sensitivity (alpha blockers, beta-blockers, vasodilators) bleeding gums

(Calcium Channel Blockers) and obesity^{7, 8}. Such side effects could be so severe that they might even force the patient to stop medicines.

Very few studies have been done in the past relating hypertension and lung insult. Some of them have shown decreased pulmonary parameters^{9,10} attributable to hypertension. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is the forerunner of various systemic complications and is one of the leading causes of preventable death in developing countries¹¹. The Framingham study is one such international study that has concluded an inverse relationship between forced vital capacity (FVC) and cardiovascular diseases and mortality, particular in women¹². Other American studies have shown that FVC is a strong, inverse predictor for the development of hypertension^{13,14}. The sustained negative impact of hypertension with added use of anti-hypertensive medications, on the respiratory system probably needs to be explored better.

In India, there are many silent contributors to lung diseases especially usage of bio- mass fuel for cooking, poor socio-economic conditions, overcrowding & poor sanitation^{15, 16, 17} and vehicle exhaust. The lungs are vulnerable to assault very easily leading to reduction in the PFT values which can be picked up early if screened regularly. Are hypertension and anti- hypertensive medications silently contributing to pulmonary disease morbidity? Reduction of PFT is only an early indicator of pulmonary morbidity. The combined effects of hypertension and anti- hypertensive medications on the lungs are not well documented in Southern parts of India. The aim of our study was to compare PFT values of hypertensives with controls and also compare PFT among cases on treatment with various classes of anti- hypertensive medications. The role of gender differences and impact of waist hip ratio (WHR) on the lung functions also were taken into due consideration.

Study Design:

This case –control study was carried out over a period of 7 months spanning from February to August 2015. Hypertensive cases (n=111) and age and sex matched healthy controls (n=91) attending the Medicine outpatient department of Sree Balaji Medical College and Hospital, Chennai, India were randomly selected for our study. They were explained the benefit of enrolling in our study and written consent was obtained from the volunteers.

Hypertensives with history of hypertension more than 2 years and on regular anti-hypertensive medications were taken as cases and apparently healthy, age- matched controls with BP \leq 140/90 mmHg were the control population. Patients with positive history of active tuberculosis, bronchial asthma, respiratory infection less than 3 weeks, hemoptysis less than 3 months, ocular or abdominal surgery less than 6months, stroke / heart attack <less than 3 months, smokers, pregnancy and lactation were excluded from our study.

Materials and Methods:

The study was commenced after obtaining the Institutional ethical committee clearance. Validated questionnaire with details on anthropometry, personal habits, and particulars of drug treatment received so far was administered.

Respiratory history was taken in detail. Socio-economic status was assessed by Modified Kuppuswamy's classification¹⁸.

Blood pressure (BP) was measured thrice after a gap of 5 minutes every time in the dominant arm and the average was recorded with the usual precautions using OMRON apparatus^{19,20}. Grading of hypertension was done as per the Seventh Report of the JNC on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure²¹. PFT was assessed using EasyOne Spirometer from Pulmonary Research Laboratory of our hospital and other hospitals as per ATS guidelines²² after proper demonstration of the procedure. Best of three attempts taken. Forced Vital capacity(FVC), Forced expiratory volume at the end of the first second(FEV₁), Peak expiratory flow rate(PEFR), Predicted Forced Vital Capacity(Pred FVC), Predicted Forced expiratory volume at the end of 1st second (Pred FEV₁) were the pulmonary parameters that were measured and recorded. The cases were sub-divided into 4 groups depending on the anti- hypertensives they were using: Group I Beta blockers (BBL) (n= 14), Group II Calcium Channel blockers (CCB) (n= 18), Group III Angiotensin receptor blockers (ARB) (n=23), Group IV combination of 2 or more of these drugs (ACE inhibitors, centrally acting drugs and diuretics) (n= 38).

Statistical analysis

Data entry done manually and analysed using SPSS software 11. ANOVA done and p values <0.05 was taken as statistically significant. Pearson's correlation and students "t" test were the additional methods that helped in our statistical analysis.

Results

Our study included 93 cases and 91 apparently healthy controls both age and sex matched (between 55 to 68 years) who were on regular anti- hypertensive medications. We excluded 18 cases due to very high BP and poor and inconsistent efforts while performing PFT. The anthropometric parameters of the cases and controls of our study population are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Description of the study population

	CONTROLS (n=91)	CASES(HYPERTENSIVES)			
		Group I (n=14)	Group II (n=18)	Group III (n=23)	Group IV (n=38)
Age (yrs)	57.41 ±7.93	57.21 ±11.59	57.72 ± 8.14	54± 8.20	57 ± 9.94
Height(m)	1.63± 0.09	1.59± 0.12	1.58 ± 0.97	1.61 ± 0.08	1.63 ± 0.11
Weight(Kg)	71.93 ±15.5 4	70.6 ± 12.16	64. 47 ±10.4 0	75.85 ± 14.84	76.0 7 ± 16.5 8

Values expressed as mean± S.D

Group I Beta blockers (BBL), Group II Calcium Channel blockers (CCB), Group III Angiotensin receptor blockers (ARB), Group IV combination of 2 or more drugs.

The highest r values for height and FVC, FEV₁ being 0.52, 0.58 among cases, 0.59, 0.49 respectively among controls. The highest r values for weight and FVC, FEV₁ being 0.75, 0.16 among cases, 0.25, 0.30 respectively among controls.

Average systolic and diastolic BP of the controls was 136 ± 8.25, 84±7.14 mm Hg and that of cases was 146±9.25, 86± 6.87 mmHg. There were 55 males and 38 female cases and 66 males and 25 female controls in our study population. PFT values of the males and females were compared using students 't' test and found to be reduced among the females as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Pulmonary function tests and BP among males and females of our study population

	Males			Females		
	FVC(L)	FEV ₁ (L/sec)	FEV ₁ /FVC	FVC(L)	FEV ₁ (L/sec)	FEV ₁ /FVC
Cases	2.77 ±0.8 0	2.21 ±0.6 6	0.79 ±0.0 9	1.95 ±2.4 4	1.43 ±0.6 7	0.79 ±0.0 8
Controls	2.96 ±0.7 3	2.57 ±0.1 3	0.65 ±0.0 4	2.23 ±1.1 6	2.01 ±0.3 1	0.61 ±0.0 3

Our results showed that among 93 cases, 49 had normal PFT values, 7 had obstruction, 5 had restriction and 32 had mixed airway disease. FVC was reduced by 300 ml or more in each group and FEV₁ reduced by 0.5 L/sec or greater in each group when compared with the controls as clearly shown in Table 3. The predicted pulmonary values were also reduced in cases when compared to controls though not significant statistically.

Table 3: Pulmonary function parameters of our study population

PFT	CONTROLS (n=91)	CASES				p value
		Group I (n=14)	Group II (n=18)	Group III (n=23)	Group IV (n=38)	
FVC(L)	2.9±0.62	2.6 ± 0.97	2.38 ±0.79	2.52 ± 0.7	2.38 ± 0.88	0.026 **
FEV ₁ (L/sec)	2.57±0.49	2.03 ± 0.69	1.74 ± 0.55	2.04 ± 0.64	1.91 ± 0.75	0.000 **
FEV ₁ /FVC	0.73±0.32	0.78 ± 0.78	0.74 ± 0.16	0.8 ±0.05	0.79 ± 0.08	0.000 **
PEFR(L/min)	6.07±2.1	5 ± 2.18	4.25 ± 1.90	6.33 ± 2.27	5.26 ± 2.57	0.038 **
Pred FVC(L)	90.07±15.58	86.07 ± 36.39	83.56 ± 22.71	77 ± 18.35	72.55 ± 25.09	0.005 **
Pred FEV ₁ (L/sec)	97.63±19.86	80.71 ± 27.85	73.67± 16.38	77.35 ± 20.07	70.89 ± 22.67	0.000 **
Pred FEV ₁ /FVC	104.07±35.6 7	97.43 ± 9.86	93 ± 20.37	100.26±6. 07	99.55 ± 9.91	0.026 **

Values expressed as mean± S.D

** p value<0.05 is statistically significant.

FVC- Forced Vital Capacity

FEV₁- Forced expiratory volume at the end of 1st second

PEFR- Peak expiratory flow rate

Pred FVC- Predicted Forced Vital Capacity

Pred FEV₁- Predicted Forced expiratory volume at the end of 1st second

PFT values were significantly higher in non-obese subjects than the obese subjects (p<0.000).The subjects were categorised into four classes based on Modified Kuppaswamy's scale. There were 22 cases in Class I, 25 in Class II, 29 in Class III, 17 in Class IV and 19 controls in Class I, 22 in Class II, 34 in Class III, 16 in Class IV. There was no significant correlation between SES and PFT values of our subjects.

Discussion

Global Burden of Disease study has estimated that hypertension led to 1.6 million deaths and 33.9 million disability-adjusted life years in 2015 and is most important cause of disease burden in India²³. The magnitude of the disease is increasing on yearly basis in India. The indication for treatment of hypertension today is systolic ≥ 140 mmHg and

diastolic ≥ 90 mmHg. The WHO/ISH 2003²⁴ statement on the management of hypertension reflects in detail about the risk factors for developing hypertension, target-organ damage and associated clinical conditions, but pulmonary complications has been overlooked. Our studies not only aimed to estimate the extent of lung damage in hypertensives but also to measure the PFT in subjects taking various classes of anti-hypertensives and compare it with healthy controls.

The description of our study population is given in Table 1. Males were taller by 13 cms and heavier by 5 kgs than their female counterparts. The mean age, height and weight of the controls and cases are comparable without any significant differences. Age had negative correlation trend while height and weight showed positive trend with most of the pulmonary parameters, correlation being greatest with FEV₁, FVC, FEV₁/FVC followed by PEFr. Earlier studies from our country and other Asian countries have proven the same^{25,26,27}

There is a statistically significant decrease in FVC, FEV₁, FEV₁ / FVC ($p=0.000$) among females (both cases and controls) in our study as shown in Table 2. Studies comparing the PFT values of hypertensive cases with controls showing such gender variations are very few in South India. Amongst cases, 49 out of 55 males, were obese with WHR >0.9 and 28 out of 38 females, were obese with WHR >0.85 . Amongst controls, 50 out of 66 males were obese and 21 out of 25 females were obese. FVC, FEV₁ and FEV₁/FVC values were significantly higher in non-obese subjects than the obese subjects ($p<0.000$). Similar results have been shown by Collins et al²⁸ in normotensive subjects where they have proved that increase in upper body fat distribution (WHR >0.9) is associated with lower FVC, FEV₁ and total lung capacity.

Average systolic and diastolic BP of the controls was 136 ± 8.25 , 84 ± 7.14 mm Hg and that of cases was 146 ± 9.25 , 86 ± 6.87 mmHg. Almost 96% of the cases were taking anti-hypertensives regularly attributing to very good control of their BP. Both systolic and diastolic BP values showed negative correlation trend with FVC, FEV₁, PEFr values. FVC was reduced by 300 ml or more in each group and FEV₁ reduced by 0.5 L/sec or greater in each group when compared with the controls. Though there

was a reduction in PFT with increasing duration of hypertension, it was not statistically significant in our study. The reasons could be greater awareness among subjects in taking medications regularly, reduction of stress and adopting life style modification measures. Reduced FEV₁ and FVC in hypertensives increases the risk of cardiovascular mortality and ultimately can lead to death^{2,3}. The pathophysiology of respiratory complications in hypertension has been postulated as increased pulmonary arterial pressure and subsequent development of interstitial pulmonary edema²⁹.

Our study population were categorised into 4 classes based on Modified Kuppaswamy's scale taking into account their education, occupation, total family income and present living conditions. There were 22 cases in Class I, 25 in Class II, 29 in Class III, 17 in Class IV and 19 controls in Class I, 22 in Class II, 34 in Class III, 16 in Class IV. There was no significant correlation between socio economic status and PFT values of our subjects. Literature has shown reduction in PFT values with lower classes of socio economic status in contradiction to our study. Small sample size, high BMI, advance age group and inclusion of more female subjects could be some possible reasons for our study results. Many international studies^{30,31,32} have also demonstrated progressive decline in pulmonary parameters especially FEV₁ with decline in socio-economic status. In 2005, an Indian study by Raju et al³³ has shown 14 to 16.7% reduction in PFT values in children of parents who belonged to lower socio-economic status. Socio-economic status is one of the important determinants of health status reflecting health care affordability of an individual. Future studies warranting adjustments for these parameters are needed.

The PFT values in our present study are- among 93 healthy cases, 49 had normal PFT values, 7 had obstruction, 5 had restriction and 32 had mixed airway disease. Swati Shah¹⁰ had shown 74% with obstruction, 13% with restriction, 13% with normal PFT values. More number of cases had mixed airway disease in the present study that can be explained because of higher female cases and also inclusion of chronic hypertensives (>15 years) in our study. The disadvantages of Swati et al study was they have not mentioned the gender difference and their study subjects gave H/O

hypertensives on an average of only 6.5 years and not greater than that.

Anti-hypertensive drugs and pulmonary function tests Pulmonary complications of BBL are well established and needless to say, they are contraindicated in COPD patients. Earlier study by³⁴ McNeil et al had proven that BBL were safe for young, uncomplicated hypertensives but recently Eva Schanbel et al⁹ have shown that BBL are well known for their adverse effects on lipid metabolism causing increase in body weight and also development of insulin resistance. But their safety in elderly hypertensives is still under debate. ACE inhibitors are commonly used in elderly subjects because of its easy tolerability, beneficial effects post myocardial infarction and relative safety in diabetic and non-diabetic nephropathy cases too. But again, the most common side effect of ACE inhibitors is dry, irritating and persistent cough, which develops in 5%–20% of patients³⁵ necessitating drug withdrawal. Thiazide diuretics causes metabolic alkalosis which can suppress the ventilatory drive, potentially worsening the degree of hypoxemia and hypercapnia as shown by Bear R et al³⁶. Literature^{37,38,39} shows CCB do not cause much pulmonary complications in hypertensive patients and hence safe to be used in elderly hypertensives. Diuretics and CCB⁴⁰ are more effective in elderly patients with isolated systolic hypertension. A German study⁴¹ showed Angiotensin II antagonists were well tolerated in patients with stage III and IV COPD, although they did not improve respiratory muscle strength or exercise capacity.

In 2001, Ross et al⁴² in a meta-analysis of 190 drug trials showed that anti-hypertensives were discontinued due to various side-effects, the order being highest with CCB (6.7%) followed by thiazide diuretics or ARB (3.1%). But, in 2011, Salpeter S et al⁴³ have concluded in their Cochrane review that cardio-selective BBL are safe in patients with reversible airway diseases and those who have compromised lung functions even before the development of hypertension. But monotherapy is not effective especially in elderly subjects as they are prone to develop side effects like obesity^{8,44} metabolic syndrome and left heart failure. There are other contradicting studies and a the lung functions of all hypertensive patients

irrespective of the class of anti-hypertensive medications they prescribe. It is difficult to assess whether hypertension alone or its medications or a combination of both are the cause for the reduced lung functions. Large scale multivariate regression analysis studies are needed to throw more light on this issue.

REFERENCES

1. Kearney PM, Whelton M, Reynolds K, Muntner P, Whelton PK, He J. Global burden of hypertension: analysis of worldwide data. *Lancet* 2005; 365(9455):217-23.
2. Engstrom G, Hedblad B, Valind S, Janzon C. Increased incidence of myocardial infarction and stroke in hypertensive men with reduced lung function. *J Hypertens* 2001; 19: 295-301.
3. Wannamethee SG, Shaper AG, Ebrahim S. Respiratory function and risk of stroke. *Stroke* 1995; 26: 2004-10.
4. Keane WF, Eknoyan G. Proteinuria, albuminuria, risk, assessment, detection and elimination (PARADE): apposition paper for the national kidney foundation. *Am J Kidney Dis* 1999; 3: 1004-1010.
5. Yoshika T, Rennke HG, Salant DJ et al. Role of abnormally high transmural pressure in the permselectivity defect of glomerular capillary wall: a study in early passive Heymann nephritis. *Circ Res* 1987; 61: 531-538.
6. Wang S, Xu L, Jonas JB, Wang YS, Wang YX, You QS et al. Five year incidence of retinal microvascular abnormalities and associations with arterial hypertension. The Beijing eye study 2001/2006. *Ophthalmology* 2012; 119(12): 2592-9.
7. Nguyen Q, Dominguez J, Nguyen L, Gullapalli N. Hypertension Management: An Update. *Am Health Drug Benefits* 2010; 3(1): 47-56.
8. Bray GA. Overweight is risking fate: definition, classification, prevalence, and risks. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 1987; 499: 14–28.
9. Eva Schnabel, Dennis Nowak, Sabine Brasche, Erich Wichmann, Joachin Heinrich. Association between lung functions, hypertension and blood pressure medication. *Respir Med* 2011; 105: 727-733.

10. Swati Shah, Mohiudddin Shaikh, Yogesh Gupta et al. Pulmonary function tests in hypertension. *IJPSR* 2014; 5(7): 338-343.
11. Pauwels RA, Buist AS, Calverley PM, Jenkins CR, Hued SS. Global strategy for the diagnosis, management and prevention of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. NHLBI/WHO Global initiative for chronic obstructive lung disease (GOLD) workshop summary. *Am J Respir critical care Med* 2001; 163: 1256-76.
12. Kannel WB, Hubert H, Lew EA. Vital capacity as a predictor of cardiovascular disease: the Framingham study. *Am Heart J* 1983; 105: 311e5.
13. Selby JV, Friedman GD, Quesenberry Jr CP. Precursors of essential hypertension: pulmonary function, heart rate, uric acid, serum cholesterol, and other serum chemistries. *Am J Epidemiol* 1990; 131: 1017e27.
14. Sparrow D, Weiss ST, Vokonas PS, Cupples LA, Ekerdt DJ, Colton T. Forced vital capacity and the risk of hypertension. The Normative Aging Study. *Am J Epidemiol* 1988; 127: 734e41.
15. Balakrishnan K, Sankar S, Parikh J et al. Daily average exposures to respirable particulate matter from combustion of biomass fuels in rural households of southern India. *Environ Health Perspect* 2002; 110: 1069-75.
16. Balakrishnan K, Sankar S, Padmavathi R, Meshia S, Smith KR. Exposures to respirable particulate matter associated with household fuel use in Andhra Pradesh, India. *J Expo Anal Environ* 2004; 14: S14-25.
17. Sumit Kumar Gautam, R. Suresh, Ved Prakash Sharma, Meena Sehgal. Indoor air quality in the rural India, *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal* 2013; 24(2): 244-255.
18. Gururaj, Maheswaran. Kuppaswamy's Socio-economic scale: A revision of income parameter for 2014. *Int J Recent Trends Technol* 2014; 11(1): 1-2.
19. Markandu N, Whitcher F, Arnold A, Carney C. The mercury sphygmomanometer should be abandoned before it is proscribed. *Journal of Human Hypertension* 2000; 14(1): 31-36.
20. Messelbech J. Sutherland L. Applying environmental product design to biomedical products research. *Environ Health Perspect* 2000; 108(6):997-1002.
21. www.nhlbi.nih.gov/files/docs/guidelines/jnc7full.pdf (15/05/2018)
22. American Thoracic Society. Lung function testing: Selection of reference values and interpretative strategies. Official statement of the American Thoracic Society. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1991; 144: 1202-18.
23. Rajeev Gupta, Denis Xavier. Hypertension: The most important non communicable disease risk factor in India. *Indian Heart Journal* 2018 (In press)
24. 2003 WHO/ ISH statement on the management of hypertension, WHO International Society on hypertension Writing Group. *J Hypertens* 2003; 21(11): 1983-1992.
25. Jain SK, Gupta CK. Lung function studies in healthy men and women over forty. *Indian J Med Res* 1967; 55: 612-20.
26. Jain SK, Gupta CK. Age, height and body weight as determinants of ventilatory norms in healthy men above forty years age. *Indian J Med Res* 1967; 55: 599-606.
27. Ip MS, Ko FW, Lau AC, Yu WC, Tang KS, Choo K, et al. Updated spirometric reference values for adult Chinese in Hong Kong and implications on clinical utilization. *Chest* 2006; 129: 384-92.
28. Lynell C, Philip H, Jerome W, Eugene F, Alan P. The effect of body fat distribution on pulmonary function tests. *Chest* 1995; 107: 1298-1302.
29. Wu Y, Volmar W.M, Buist AS, T Sai R, Cen R, Wu X et al. Relationship between lung function and BP in Chinese men and women of Beijing and Guangzhou. *Int J Epiderm* 1998; 27: 49-56.
30. Mathew J Hegewald, Robert O Crapo. Socio-economic status and lung function. *Chest* 2007; 132(5): 1608-1614.
31. Wheeler BW, Ben-Shlomo Y. Environmental equity, air quality, socioeconomic status and respiratory health: a linkage analysis of routine data from the health survey for England. *J Epidemiol Community Health* 2005; 59: 948-954.
32. Ecob R, Smith GD. Income and health. What is the nature of the relationship? *Soc Sci Med* 1999; 48: 693-705.

33. Raju PS, Prasad KV, Ramana YV et al. Influence of SES on lung function and prediction equations in Indian children. *Pediatr Pulmonol* 2005; 39: 528- 536.
34. McNeill RS. Effect of a beta-adrenergic-blocking agent, propranolol, on asthmatics. *Lancet* 1964; 2: 1101e2.
35. Israili ZH, Hall WD. Cough and angioneurotic edema associated with angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor therapy. A review of the literature and pathophysiology. *Ann Intern Med.* 1992; 117(3): 234–242.
36. Bear R, Goldstein M, Phillipson E, et al. Effect of metabolic alkalosis on respiratory function in patients with chronic obstructive lung disease. *Can Med Assoc J* 1977; 117(8): 900–903.
37. Patakas D, Maniki E, Tsara V, Dascalopoulou E. Nifedipine treatment of patients with bronchial asthma. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 1987; 79(6): 959–963.
38. Schwartzstein RS, Fanta CH. Orally administered nifedipine in chronic stable asthma. Comparison with an orally administered sympathomimetic. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1986; 134(2): 262–265.
39. Ann Twiss M, Harman E, Chesrown S, Hendeles L. Efficacy of calcium channel blockers as maintenance therapy for asthma. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 2002; 53(3): 243–249.
40. Morgan TO, Anderson AI, MacInnis RJ. ACE inhibitors, beta-blockers, calcium blockers, and diuretics for the control of systolic hypertension. *Am J Hypertens* 2001 Mar; 14(3): 241-7.
41. Andreas S, Herrmann-Lingen C, Raupach T, et al. Angiotensin II blockers in obstructive pulmonary disease: a randomised controlled trial. *Eur Respir J* 2006; 27(5): 972–979.
42. Ross SD, Akhras KS, Zhang S, Rozinsky M, Nalysnyk L. Discontinuation of antihypertensive drugs due to adverse events: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Pharmacotherapy* 2001; 21: 940-53.
43. Salpeter SR, Ormiston TM, Salpeter EE. Cardioselective beta blockers for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Cochrane database Syst Rev* 2005; 19(4).Art No.CD003566.
44. Davis BR, Oberman A, Blaufox MD et al. Effect of antihypertensive therapy on weight loss: the Trial of Antihypertensive Interventions and Management Research Group. *Hypertension* 1992; 19: 393–399.

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